

Development Of Self-Compacting Concrete Made With Locally Available Materials In Different W/C Ratio And Different Gradation Of Fine Aggregate

Author's Details: K. Azad^{a*}, B. Barua^b, A. Hossain^c

^aLecturer, Port City International University, Chattogram, Bangladesh

^bGraduate Student, Port City International University, Chattogram, Bangladesh

^cGraduate Student, Port City International University, Chattogram, Bangladesh

Abstract

The need for high-performance concrete with improved workability, higher strength, and greater longevity has risen in recent years to satisfy the current requirements for structural construction. Consequently, the development of self-compacting concrete in Bangladesh has recently become one of the most significant developments in the construction industry. To place and be able to flow under its weight, this innovative concrete does not require additional vibration. The main objective of this study was to investigate the SCC developed in this study using locally available materials incorporating different W/C ratios and different FM of fine aggregate in terms of both fresh and mechanical properties. For the necessary tests, nine mixtures were prepared with different W/C ratios and different FM of fine aggregate, and the same Superplasticizer dosages. Slump flow, V-funnel, L-box, and T50 were involved in the fresh property tests. However, the experimental results showed that with the reduction of the W/C ratio, compressive strength was improved and the FM of fine aggregate shift is not too much of a compressive strength effect. In comparison, almost all fresh property prices meet the ACI requirements and the W/C ratio 0.4 and 0.45 and 0.5 meet the design specifications of the ACI mix. The compressive strength test is tested in concrete age is 7, 14, and 28 days total of 27 cubes are crushed in the universal testing machine. Therefore, it is invariably possible to use locally available materials to build SCC for sustainable development in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Self-compacting concrete, Superplasticizer, W/C ratio, FM of fine aggregate, Workability, Fresh and Mechanical property.

1. Introduction

Concrete is the most adaptable heterogeneous development materials and force of infrastructural improvement of any country. Self-compacting concrete (SCC) is the most broadly utilized development work far and wide. The idea of SCC Was proposed in 1986 by teacher Hajime Okamura, yet the model was first evolved in 1986 in Japan, at the University of Tokyo, as in [7]. SCC as sketched out by ACI Committee 237 (2007) is "profoundly stream prepared, non-isolating solid which will unfurl into place, fill the formwork, and epitomize the fortification with none mechanical combination". Self-compacting concrete is a superior solid which stream under its load through the confined segment without isolation and draining and doesn't need and outside vibration for the combination [8]. To dodge isolation and seeping of Self-compacting solid we utilized superplasticizer admixture. . SCC mix was designed according to ACI committee 237 and mixed under two different environmental temperatures (22 and 44 C). The slump flow and passing ability of Self-compacting Concrete of Mixture were slightly lost between 0-15 minutes. The results also showed that the addition of 0.5% by weight of powders superplasticizer after 30 minutes [9]. The Compressive strength of SCC is 90 days. The water Cement ratio influences the strength property of Self-Compacting Concrete but it's no effect on the plastic properties of Self-Compacting Concrete[10].

In this works, we additionally endeavor to improve understanding about the advancement of SCC utilizing locally accessible materials in Bangladesh. The significant target of this examination we were to explore the SCC made with locally accessible materials as far as both new and mechanical properties and to complete the investigation on the graphical correlations of SCC with various w/c proportions and diverse degrees of fine total and same portions of synthetic admixture. We likewise graphical correlations have been created dependent on trial brings about a request to propose the reasonable w/c proportion and degree of the fine total for the moreover advancement of SCC keeping up its usefulness with no isolation and dying.

2. Methodology

2.1. Material property

In our work, the locally available stone aggregate crash- stone type was used as a coarse aggregate. Fine aggregate collected from the local market, Sylhet sand, and local river flow sand was utilized. Portland cement was the cement used for this study. Drinking tap water was used to mix. The chemical admixture we are using: our work involved HWRA (Highly Water Reducing Admixture). The mix-design for SCC is ACI specification and the ratio of Cement: Sand: Coarse Aggregate (1:1.5:3) was maintained constant, while the W /C ratio varied from 0.40 to 0.5 and the FM varied from 2.76 to 3.8, respectively. A total of nine cases were investigated.

Items	CA (Avg. Value)
Specific Gravity (SSD)	2.88
Fineness Modulus (FM)	7.2
Dry rodded unit weight(OD)	101.55lb/ ft ³
Surface Moisture	1%
Water absorption Capacity	2%

Table:01 Coarse Aggregate Property (Stone chips)

Sample ID	W/C ratio	FM of Fine aggregate	FM of Coarse aggregate	Mixing ratio (C:FA: CA)	HWRA (per bag) (ml)
Sam-1	0.4	3.38	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-2	0.4	2.97	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-3	0.4	2.75	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-4	0.45	3.38	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-5	0.45	2.97	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-6	0.45	2.74	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-7	0.5	3.38	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-8	0.5	2.97	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml
Sam-9	0.5	2.74	7.2	1:1.5:3	2ml

Table:02 Mixture proportion of SCC

2.2. Mixing and Casting Details

In the production of SCC, the mixing duration is important. Concrete is a composite mixture consisting of cement, sand, and coarse concrete mixing aggregate. Design is the procedure for finding the correct quantities of these materials to achieve the desired strength. Precise, economical construction for large constructions. The materials were mixed in a free fall mixer of 200 liters per type of concrete. Based on the total volume of concrete, the required amount of segment materials was estimated according to the mix design and measured using digital weight balance. At the time of mixing the coarse and fine aggregates were in SSD condition. After 70% of the water was added into the mixer, the dry components were mixed effectively until their uniform distribution was achieved, and the superplasticizer was mixed with the remaining water to obtain a homogeneous square sample (6 inches X 6 inches) ready to determine the hardened properties. They cast the specimens without any vibration or compaction. They were removed and stored in water for 7 days, 14 days, 21 days, and 28 days for healing after 24 hours of casting.

2.3 Testing Method

2.3.1. Slump Flow Test

The Slump-stream test is the least complex and most generally received test strategy for assessing the filling/stream capacity nature of self-compacting concrete in the lab and at building destinations (ASTM C

1611). Fundamentally, the droop stream test is utilized to survey the level of free progression of SCC without checks. On lifting the droop cone loaded up with concrete the solid streams. The normal distance across the solid circle is an estimation of the stream capacity of the solid. In this examination, subsequently, the breadth of the solid streaming out of the droop cone was estimated by ascertaining the normal of two oppositely estimated widths to decide the droop stream of SCC.

2.3.2. T50 Test

The time T50 cm is an optional sign of stream capacity of cement. Essentially, this test is a piece of droop stream test. It gauges the time taken by the solid in seconds from the moment the cone is lifted to the moment when even stream ranges to the width of 500mm.

Figure 1. T50 Test.

2.3.3. V – Funnel Test

The fresh concrete's flow capability can also be tested with the V-funnel test, where the flow time is measured. This test device consists of a funnel with a rectangular cross-section (top size is 495 mm by 75 mm and the bottom opening is 75 mm by 75 mm) and total height is 572 mm with a straight section of 150 mm long. In this study, the funnel was filled with about 12 liters of fresh concrete and measured as illustrated in Figure 3, the time taken to flow through the apparatus. Less flow time indicates greater flow capacity. Besides, V-funnel was also used to measure T5min, which indicates the tendency to segregate. When the concrete shows up Segregation, greatly increases the flow time. However, in this method, the funnel was refilled with Concrete and left to settle for 5 minutes.

Figure 2. V -Funnel Test.

2.3.4. L – Box Test

The L-box test can be used to assess SCC's ability to pass through narrow spaces, even with the congested area of reinforcement (Bhuva et al., 2011). Filled the vertical section of the apparatus with 14-liter fresh concrete and after one minute the concrete was allowed to pass through the reinforcement to the horizontal section. When the concrete was in a stable condition, the concrete height at the end of the horizontal section (H2) and the concrete vestige height at the vertical section (H1) was individually measured to calculate the blocking ratio $H2/H1$, to observe the fresh SCC's passing ability. These are known as the T20 and T40.

Figure 3. L-Box Test.

2.3.3. Compressive Strengths Test

The Compressive strength tests are specific SSC specimens as per ASTM C39 respectively universal testing machine.

3. Result and Discussion

A total of nine samples are tested in fresh property and it's summarized in Table 03.

Sample no	Slump flow (mm)	T50 Test Time (sec)	L -Box Test Blocking Ratio (H2/H1)	V-funnel Test, Time(sec)
Sam-1	570	5.5	0.69	12
Sam-2	568	5	0.68	11
Sam-3	572	5	0.66	11
Sam-4	649	3	0.95	10
Sam-5	645	4	0.94	9
Sam-6	450	3.5	0.95	8
Sam-7	715	2	0.98	5
Sam-8	717	2	0.97	4
Sam-9	718	2	0.97	4

Table: 03 Fresh property test results of SCC

Figure 2. V -Funnel Test.

The slumping flow of the self-compacting concrete range of 568 to 718 mm is part of our work. The default value of the ACI range slump flow test is 500-700 mm. We see that sample 7, 8, 9 isn't the standard range. The slump flow is related to the ratio of water to cement used when the ratio of water to cement

decreases and FM is graded on the wall when the flow length decreases.

Figure 2. T50 test variation Graph

The test time range of T50 for our study is 2 to 7 seconds. The SCC T50 Test Time standard value is 2 to 10 seconds. The standard value is filled with all of the samples. The test time of T50 is associated with superplasticizer dosages.

Figure 2. V-funnel test variation Graph

V-Funnel Test, which shows the segregation trend. The V-flow time ranging from 4 to 12 seconds. Where the sample 1 value is similar to the standard value of 12sec, which indicates the good flowability of SCC. The W/C ratio is up, the V-flow test time is down, indicating that the high w/c ratio & better flowability. The FM variation of fine aggregate is not great in the capacity of the flow.

Figure 2.L-Box test variation Graph

The passing ability of the SCC is observed in this test. The variation of the blocking ratio (H1/H2). The standard blocking ratio for the ACI range is 0.8 to 1. In our work, we ensure that the blocking ratio range is 0.66 to 0.98. For Sample 1, 2 & 3 the standard value is not required.

In our study, we observed that when the water-cement ratio increases the flowability and passing ability is good as well as segregation resistance is also good. But the variation FM of fine aggregate is not too much variation of fresh property for Self –compacting concrete.

Figure 2. Compressive Strength test variation Graph

The final process to conclude that the different specimen was over the ACI mix design is compared to the different range of W/C ratio and FM of fine aggregate after testing the fresh property and hundred SCC now, from the study it is concluded that it was good. We observed the age of concrete compressive strength at 28 days is the Sam-1 is highest and Sam-9 is lowest.

The compressive strength is the most important parameter of Self-compacting concrete. In our study, we observed when the SCC water-cement ratio increases the compressive strength is decreasing. But the variation of FM of fine aggregate is not too much variation of compressive strength of Self-compacting concrete. The test results of compressive strength are satisfactory of design value.

4. Conculation

- The self-compacting concrete (SCC) achieved consistency and self-compact ability under its weight, without any outside vibration or compaction, by using the Slump flow, T50, and V-funnel tests.
- The SCC also gained satisfactory passing and filling capacity through the use of L-box tests even in the presence of congested reinforcement without any further segregation or bleeding.
- From this study, it can be concluded that the ratio of water to cement and FM of fine aggregate has a significant effect on both SCC's fresh and hard characteristics for SCC generation.

5. Acknowledgements

We are thankful to the staff of the concrete laboratory for their help and cooperation during experimental work. The research work was conducted with the laboratory facilities provided by the Department of Civil Engineering, (PCIU).

References

- i. *ACI237R-07 Self-Consolidation Concrete*, American, Farmington, USA.
- ii. *ASTM C604 - 02(2012) Standard Test Method for True Specific Gravity.*
- iii. *ASTM C1403 - 15 Standard Test Method for Rate of Water Absorption.*

- iv. *ASTMC 33 - C 33M - 16e1 Standard Specification for Concrete Aggregates.*
- v. *ASTM C-778 - 13 Standard Specifications for Standard Sand.*
- vi. *ASTM C 39 - C 39M – 17 Standard Test Method for Compressive Strength of Cylindrical Concrete Specimens.*
- vii. *Okamura H., Ozawa K., “Mix Design for Self-Compacting Concrete”, Concrete Library of Japanese Society of Civil Engineers,p.107-120, June 25, 1995.*
- viii. *Khan, R. M, Amin, F., and Ahmed, M., (2015), “Comparison of Self Compacting Concrete Using Recycled Aggregates & Normal Aggregates”, International journal of advance research in science and engineering, Vol. No.4, Issue 07 July 2015.*
- ix. *Jasim, A. T. (2014). Fresh properties of self-compacting concrete with time : September.*
- x. *Olafusi, O. S., Adewuyi, A. P., Otunla, A. I., & Babalola, A. O. (2015). Evaluation of fresh and hardened properties of self-compacting concrete. Open journal of civil engineering, 05(01), 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ojce.2015.51001>*